

Debating Peer-review

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Abstract

Peer review is deemed essential for the quality control of the publication of research. Peer review can refine a researcher and their research articles. However, peer review comes with many problems like the incompetence of the reviewers. It sometimes feels redundant and at other times, it seems too pushy from the editor's end. Using the method of autoethnography, I have identified some weaknesses including shortage of resources, motivation of reviewers, specialization, ignorance of quality control of literature review, and the blockade of innovation. Nonetheless, the peer review method will be used by journal editors until a better alternative is found. I share my experience of being peer-reviewed in seven years of my academic life in this autoethnography. The conclusion is that peer review is not the foolproof way to control the quality of review and research articles.

Keywords: Journals, quality control, research, psychology, publication

Introduction

Peer review is a process of examining a scholarly article by two or more peers for its quality control to decide if it is publishable in the journal. Peers are the experts in the specific field of research (Saughnessy et al., 2015, p.418). After a (team of) researcher(s) (and also writer[s]) sends an article, the editor of a journal checks if the article meets the objectives/theme of the journal. If it does, they send it to peer reviewers to check the industry standards of the research article along with the research. Reviewers provide feedback and researchers modify the article to be reviewed by reviewers again. If the writer can incorporate comments or defend her position, they are ultimately published by the decision of the editor. It is assumed that peer review is the primary and ubiquitous method of quality control (Tennant & Ross-Hellauer, 2020). Quality control is necessary in two regards- content and style. Unwarranted claims, unacceptable interpretations, or personal views are prevented by peer review from publication (Kelly et al., 2014). It also helps determine the validity, significance, and originality of the study. In short, peer review subjects manuscripts to expert evaluation ("Importance of Peer Review," 2014).

There are four types of peer review- single-blind review, double-blind review, triple-blind review, and open review (What is Peer Review, 2020). In single-blind reviews, reviewers' identity is kept hidden from authors. In a double-blind review, both the author and reviewers are anonymous. In

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triple-blind review, all editors, reviewers, and authors are anonymous. In an open review, both authors and reviewers are known to each other. Some journals adopt an even more transparent review process.

In comparison to the standard procedure of peer-reviewing, all peer-reviewed journals in Nepal are not peer-reviewed in a true sense; only a few of them are. For example, my article based on action research (Adhikari, 2022b) was unilaterally altered by the journal editors of a Nepali journal and the quality of the publication got a degradation rather than upgradation. I opine that, in the present context, the unreviewing journals should also continue as publication is more important. We can hope that we can search for quality after there is a significant increase in quantity.

Statement of the Problems

Peer review is the only way being used globally to ensure quality control of the research articles. However, there are some problems with the peer review process. It is not foolproof and hence the pace of science has slowed down. If the problems related to peer review can be addressed, the quality of journal articles can be increased even more.

Objectives

This autoethnography aims to identify the problems associated with the peer review process idiosyncratically. Figuring out the problems helps pave a path to their solution. Alternatively, peer review may be replaced with some better method to ensure the quality control of research papers. This research also briefly presents the merits of peer review based on my experiences of publication.

Methods

This paper is the outcome of my autoethnography in which researchers' lived experiences can be used to transform the practice like research and teaching (Belbase et al., 2008). The researchers themselves are the objects of study. In this method, the researcher can connect their narrative with the broader social and cultural context (Adams et al., 2015) to critique practices using reflexivity. I reviewed my published articles remaining on my computer or OneDrive (a cloud storage service) and recollected the experiences related to them. I also reviewed some auxiliary artifacts related to the published articles. I have analyzed my memories of experiences and figured out some themes/patterns and presented them here. This paper presents the researcher's perspective mainly rather than a reviewer's.

Results

There are many positive things about peer review. The constructive feedback is the base for learning things and building on the comments from reviewers, a researcher can improve their research article or rarely research itself. A researcher or a team of researchers may miss out on some "common sense" elements or insert silly/minor weaknesses. With an examination from reviewers, these can be spotted. The nuanced perspective from reviewers can enrich the research/review paper. An important benefit of peer review is to be updated about the current trends/conventions in the related field of study. The researchers can refine themselves with the help of peer review.

Despite the above-mentioned benefits, there are many weaknesses of peer review. Some challenges of peer review are given below and described concisely. The challenges are presented in thematic forms.

Individual Reviewers

In an age when teamwork is the trend to get a research article published, why should the sole reviewers determine if the paper is publishable separately? Why should they not work in a team, too? The sole authors do not have competence on everything like design, statistics, writing, language among others except in a few cases. They should work in a team so that they can complement the skills other members do not have. There is a stark need that reviewers work in teams as well.

Quality of Journals

With the proliferation of too many journals, anybody can be a reviewer or even an author. Even the journal may not go through the quality control process. The mushrooming of predatory journals is the result of a lack of regulation in the scholarly publication industry. If you check at <https://portal.issn.org/> feeding an ISSN number, ISSN International Center's website cannot distinguish which journal is genuine and which is predatory/phony. In the globalized era, a Nepali researcher can get published from Croatia, the USA, Romania, Turkey, Brazil, China, or any other country in the world.

Shortage of Resources

Many budding journals have a lack of articles. They hardly find journals. They hardly find reviewers; sometimes, they find ones from the recommendation of authors themselves. The articles are commented/criticized harshly oftentimes but they are obligated to publish them ultimately despite lack of correction on the part of the authors because of a dearth of original articles. A coordinating staff at Tribhuvan University Journal (TUJ) told me that it was extremely difficult for them to find reviewers for articles written about psychology.

Dearth of Reviewers

After publishing two articles- one review and one theory- on accidents, I received a request to review a research article on accident. After my team published research paper on the mental health issue of older adults in an acclaimed journal, I got a request to review a research article related to the same issue from another acclaimed journal. I did not consider myself to be an expert; I thought myself to be a learner. It may be an impostor syndrome! However, my receiving of peer-review requests from highly acclaimed international journals indicates that they have a dearth of experienced reviewers.

Motivation of Reviewers

Generally, reviewers are not paid. Except for reviewing by intrinsic motivation, reviewers are likely to comment on the paper swiftly and superficially. The only motivational factor to review is to learn more skills of research during the review process or to get connected to the branded journal.

Diversity in Specialization

Now, the sciences including psychology are in the rapid process of development. A consequence is the deep specialization of the fields with the growth of sciences. Psychology will be more specialized and new perspectives will emerge down the line (Feldman, 2015, p.26). A researcher is an expert in the field. She needs to be reviewed by somebody who may not be the expert. Even though reviewers are specialized in an area, they may be assigned to review articles written from different specializations. In such a situation, the brand image of the reviewer like professorship, high position in an organization, or awards received by the reviewer may impact the editor's choice to comply with their decision to retain or reject the articles. For example, my research related to the construction and validation of usability (Adhikari, 2023) was apparently reviewed by psychologists who specialized in fields other than Industrial and Organizational Psychology (or Human Factors). Both of the two reviewers of the research article failed to notice the theoretical framework in the article that was existent in the first draft itself. They probably evaluated the process and missed out on the content. They did the quality control, but partially.

Late Publication

In the process of review, the researchers may have to modify the article several times. This dillydallies the publication. The decision-making that should have been benefitted by research output might be missed. In extreme cases, researchers may be asked to change the design of the research entirely. So, the publication is intensely delayed.

Ignorance of Quality of Literature Review

Many journals do not review how literature review has been done. They just look at the citation and if it is good, they assume that the literature review must have been done well too. However, literature review, as a critical summarizing of past studies or relevant literature, is subpar in several cases. Tracing back to what has been cited and how it has been cited should be a part of quality control.

Figure 1. Reviewer's dissatisfaction about use of in-text citation when the two first authors had same surname. This instance shows the reviewer's lack of update on APA 7th style. I do not question reviewer's qualification but the lack of update is seen as a trend as it has happened to me in cases of other articles also.

Over smart Editors/Reviewers

Some editors, like senior professors or overconfident people, are not welcoming to new ideas. They think what they have learned is good, enough, and right. They do not update themselves to new methods or technologies and take a rigid stance to reject papers with new approaches, methods, or technologies. I continuously sent two qualitative research articles to TUJ but the editors did not respond to the article. I hoped to get rejection mail if they did not deem my article fit for their journal. I generally hope to get reasonable causes of rejection also. The culture of responsiveness to customer is lacking in almost all Nepali governmental offices but I infer that their disinterest in qualitative research was the main reason. I have received calls, not emails, from the very journal for the articles that had the possibility of getting published. I recall a fellow researcher blaming an ethical review board of not focusing on ethical aspects and commenting on other details of the proposal.

- Demographic details of the participants is missing
- CFA and EFA on the same data set need explanation and support for doing so, as it is not generally accepted.
- EFA followed by CFA is not generally accepted
- Before deleting the items, the author could have checked the modification index and tried covariance between variables.

Figure 1. Comments for my article published in TUJ (Adhikari, 2023). Some comments are constructive. However, some comments are ineffective, if not devastating.

Monistic Mindset in Science

There is no single way to do science, especially behavioral science like psychology, correctly. New trends always emerge. For example, significance testing was considered classy in statistics some decades ago. Now, it is thought necessary but insufficient by some. Some people advocate to rule out its use from research. Bayesian statistics has arisen as an alternative to classical statistics. Few reviewers would be ready to master all these multitudes of possibilities. Some reviewers/editors stick to the traditional monistic mindset of doing science and thwart the possibility of new methods or styles. They are not tolerant of pluralism in science.

Stifling the Innovation

It is seen that journal editors and reviewers religiously believe in science or the way of doing it. When the editors and reviewers ritualistically stick to the tradition, they may stifle the innovation in industry. The new ideas, techniques, and methods may get nibbed in the bud. In the name of peer review, the journals may promote the unscientific practice themselves. Open-mindedness is the essence of a scientific attitude (Branscombe & Baron, 2017, p. 22). Moreover, what we call science is also a culture and convention at the same time. Quantitative research, what we call scientific, is founded on positivism. Positivism, as a philosophical framework, was intuitionally proposed by some philosophers, say Auguste Comte (Hergenhahn & Henley, 2014, p. 158). In other words, what we claim scientific lays on unscientific ground. So, providing a little space for unconventional write-ups should not be a bother to the people in journals.

Review of Research or Paper

Most of the time, the peer-review process is too concerned with the quality of the research paper rather than the research itself. If the focus is on paper, it is the aesthetics' and technicality's quality being ensured by the peer review. Some alternatives like pre-registering (Simmons et al., 2021) are being introduced to ensure research quality by controlling HARKing (Hypothesizing After the Results are Known) and p-hacking. p-hacking is claiming non-significant results as significant by changing p-values (Angelika & Schönbrodt, 2023).

I myself do not object to HARKing even though accepting the process makes its label invalid. In this process, I notice the exploratory design in quantitative research. You may ethically and genuinely collect data and explore the relationship among variables and then present the results in a research paper. In doing so, we may discover the relationship between variables in a way we may not have intuitively imagined. This way of research becomes the inductive approach to doing the quantitative research. However, ethical reporting requires that researchers do not present post hoc hypotheses as a priori ones (Rubin, 2017). In rejecting the articles without the theoretical framework, the top-tier journals are thwarting the chances of the emergence of new theories via quantitative research designs. One of my team's articles (Adhikari & McLaren, 2023) was rejected by a Q1 journal for that very reason. With the fear of being rejected again, we had to add a theory as a framework in this research to get published in the next journal.

Lack of Retrogressive Effect

Some comments from peer reviewers may question the design of the research. It is not possible in quantitative research to alter the design retrogressively. However, the researcher is under pressure to get published. The researchers chose an alternative journal and reframed the wording of the report to evade similar remarks (and rejection) from another journal.

My Experience

My first publications (Adhikari, 2014, 2015, 2017b) were grand. The newspaper article was culled by an editor. The review article was rigorously peer-reviewed and published more than 12 months after submission. The book chapter was peer-reviewed but it got published relatively more easily. After I was selected into Tribhuvan University as a faculty, I turned to my past studies to get them published. At least three papers (Adhikari, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c; Adhikari & Acharya, 2019) were published in predatory journals without my knowledge that they were predators, even though I did not pay them any money. All of these publishers pretended that they based their publications on the peer-review process. I get several spams still but ignore them. I am proud that I have been published in good journals recently (Adhikari, 2017a, 2019, 2020; Adhikari & Poudel, 2020). An article published in 2020 was modified to the extent that I was too dissatisfied with the final outcome as it was totally different than what I had intended. The reviewers were too pushy to alter its statistical aspects so I had to change the title. Nonetheless, I insisted on getting published owing to my obligation for career growth. In an article (Adhikari, 2017a), the reviewers were

not welcoming/updated to qualitative research. They forced me to add more research participants later. The outcome of the research seemed like a mixed-method design rather than qualitative. I am sure that I can get published in top-tier journals in the coming days. However, I believe that getting published is more important than choosing a journal brand for now in the Nepali context concerning the paucity of studies in psychology. Number of citations and impact factor of journals are secondary.

How to cite this Book (APA 7):

Adhikari, Y., Shrestha, S., & Sigdel, K. (2022). *Nepalese Psychology: Volume One*. Evincepub. India: chhattisgarh.

Figure 2. This picture, which presents suggestions from editors to readers on the way to cite the book they published, shows a lapse on the part of editors. There are mistakes in more than one place. The editors' lack of update is conspicuous in this publication. They seem to have a hangover of the 6th edition of the Publication Manual of APA to mention the location of publisher and they present themselves as writers when they are editors. I mention this example because I was also a part of this book (Adhikari, 2022a).

Discussion

Peer review is popular and rightly so. However, its usefulness has not been appropriately proven. It is just a convention to peer-review journal articles. Even though peer review lacks scientific verification for effectiveness, most people in the scientific community believe that it is necessary. There are several problems including a lack of holistic competence among reviewers and the time-consuming nature of the review process. Peer review is necessary but a better alternative is desirable for the quality control of the published works in scientific journals.

Conclusion

Peer review has many advantages and also many flaws at the same time. The alternative way to maintain quality control is desirable. Nonetheless, the use of peer review will not get obsolete soon despite its lapses. This paper showed some weaknesses. They can be addressed by journals to improve the quality of research papers and accelerate the development of science finally.

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त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय

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प्रकाशन समिति

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मानविकी तथा सामाजिक शास्त्र सङ्कायको वर्तमान संरचना र महाविद्यालय (स्कूल) को आधार <i>गोविन्दप्रसाद शर्मा (सुकुम शर्मा)</i>	१५
अतृप्त उपन्यासमा सामाजिक मनोविज्ञानको प्रयोग <i>दीपकप्रसाद गौतम</i>	२४
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